

Twitter Sentiment Analysis Using Deep Learning Algorithm

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Abstract— Sentiment analysis is the process of using NLP (Natural Language Processing) to interpret text, and analyse the subjective information which can be contained in a text document concerning a particular topic. User generated data is accumulating exponentially especially through social networking sites like Twitter. This user generated content illustrates various user sentiments and emotions. This document introduces a method of analysing twitter data and classifies them into 3 sentiments (positive, negative, neutral) by using deep learning approach. The system extracts the twitter data, performs NLP processing on it, (such as removing stop-words and tokenizing the content) then applies deep learning models for classification. A web interface is developed which enables users to input a twitter stream and obtains the classification result.

Keywords— Sentiment Analysis, Deep Learning, Twitter Data, Natural Language Processing, Text Classification, Social Media Analytics.

I. INTRODUCTION

Social media networks are growing at a phenomenal rate, which in turn generate massive amounts of text data each day. One of the most popular such networks is twitter, on which users share their opinions, feelings and attitudes regarding issues like products, events, society etc. Organizations, businesses and researchers could use this information of people's opinions in order to gauge public opinion and trends. But with the enormous number of tweets sent daily, manual analyzing of such a body of information is a challenging and labor-intensive task.

Sentiment Analysis (Opinion mining) is an NLP task where the emotional sense of a given text is extracted. This text can be then categorized as positive, negative, neutral, etc. Sentiment Analysis has conventionally been carried out using machine learning techniques which would intuitively not be good in contextuality or relation between words. Deep learning has far excelled traditional machine learning techniques on text tasks and this is probably because deep learning models have a higher capability to automatically learn features from large amount of data.

In this paper, we developed a deep learning-based sentiment analysis system, which is designed for performing the tweet data processing efficiently to predict the sentiments of tweet. The processes of gaining the tweet data are conducted, which include data acquisition, data preprocessing, feature extraction and model training. In this system, deep learning-based models are used to improve the efficiency and performance of sentiment classification. The web interface is provided to allow the user to interact and get the prediction for tweet input text easily.

The system which is presented has the purpose to define a system to analyze large volumes of data that are available

on social media, in an accurate and efficient way. Such a system will use deep learning algorithms and techniques from the domain of Natural Language Processing in order to analyze the trend of opinion of the public about any kind of topics and the sentiment. Such type of applications is useful for businessman, scientists and policymakers for the detection of public opinion for any topic of interest.

II. RELATED WORK

Opinion mining and sentiment analysis has been a subject of active research for a number of years now and this is due to the large growth in social networks. An early and comprehensive piece on opinion mining and sentiment analysis was conducted by Bo Pang and Lillian Lee (2008) where they show how machine learning methods could classify sentiments from text and they also shown how text produced by web users can be analyzed.

Then, Yoon Kim (2014) suggested the use of Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for sentence classification. The model has achieved remarkable performance in text classification and sentiment analysis by learning valuable features automatically from text.

There is also an article by Alec Radford et al., that covers some current deep neural networks architectures in NLP and show that deep learning is a good approach for word-context relations and for enhancing the sentiment analysis task.

The suggested system is based on such studies, and it has adopted deep learning methods to analyze tweet data and predict the sentiment with high accuracy. This system employs recent natural language processing techniques as well as deep learning techniques, to make the prediction of sentiment in social media data more efficient and accurate.

III. METHODOLOGY

The architecture that we have proposed is used for carrying out the twitter sentiment analysis using deep learning techniques. The following steps are involved in this process - data collection, data preprocessing, feature extraction, model training and sentiment classification. Each and every phase is essential in the improvement of performance and accuracy of sentiment analysis system. The order in which the whole system is processed is data collection, data preprocessing and feature extraction and deep learning model training to classify the tweet sentiment to positive, negative, neutral.

A. Data Collection

In stage 1, we obtain Twitter data by collecting publicly available datasets or utilizing Twitter APIs. This dataset has a large number of tweets with various sentiments and opinions, which are then used as the input for training and

testing the sentiment analysis model. Such dataset will contain the tweets text and their corresponding sentiment labels (positive, negative, neutral).

B. Data Preprocessing

Preprocessing is the phase of cleaning up the data collected (tweets). There are multiple steps of cleaning and these include transforming into lower case, removing special characters and stop words, tokenizing and etc. This is a required preprocessing step so that the data is clean and the model which will be trained by deep learning will perform better.

C. Feature Extraction

The pre-processed text data is now converted to some numerical format that machine learning & deep learning models can understand. Words are converted to a feature vector through word embedding or vectorization methods. A vector consists of words, a relation of word to word is learned, so that the models can get the better patterns from. This feature extraction plays an essential role for high performance.

D. Deep Learning Model

This is the step where we use deep learning model to do tweet sentiment classification. Deep learning methods work well on capturing complex, context-dependent information from texts and in this project, we use LSTMs or some type of neural network for sentiment classification tasks. Deep learning model can learn the given text from us is either positive, negative or neutral sentiment according to the features we have extracted from tweet data set. With its good ability of automatically learning from textual data, deep learning gives higher classification accuracy than traditional machine learning.

E. System Architecture

There are few stages in proposed model for Twitter sentiment analysis. That are data collection, data preprocessing, feature extraction, training the model, prediction the sentiment. Firstly, data is collected from Twitter and pre-processing method such as remove stop words, tokenize etc. Are performed. Then features are extracted and represented in feature vector from using feature extraction methods. The features vector is used as input in deep learning model and the model extracts the text pattern and classifies and predicts the sentiment of tweet to one of the sentiment categories. The predicted sentiment will be displayed in web-based application and user will be given to input the text of tweet and received the predicted sentiment.

The architecture of the system consists of the modules mentioned above which are interrelated to each other to do sentiment analysis on twitter data. The data acquisition is the initial phase of the system, wherein tweet data is obtained and sent to the pre-processing phase. All the noise present in the form of special characters, symbols and stop-words from the tweet data is eliminated in the pre-processing phase. The clean text data is then transformed into a numerical format using feature extraction techniques (text vectorization/word embedding). This extracted feature data is provided as input to the deep learning model

that learns the text pattern and predicts the category of sentiment. This prediction is shown on the web interface.

Fig. 1. Architecture of the Proposed Twitter Sentiment Analysis System

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section covers the performance analysis of proposed twitter sentiment analysis system. The developed model takes tweet as input and predicts the sentiment in three categories: positive, negative and neutral. From the results of proposed system, it can be observed that deep learning methods can be employed in sentiment classification. A web interface is developed which can take a tweet input and provide the sentiment based on the input in real time.

A. Web Interface

Web based interface. It has been made in order to be user friendly, and so that the user may give the tweet as input text so that the text is to be given to the system for analysis. Deep learning model which is already trained uses the text of the tweet to predict its category of sentiment, it is shown to the user in the web interface so that the user is able to observe the tweets sentiment as positive, negative or neutral.

B. Experimental Results

In this page it is visualized how the created Twitter sentiment analysis system has been developed and performed. A deep learning model, that recognizes the text from a tweet, assigns the sentiment into one of the following classes; positive, negative or neutral. After the model training the trained model is tested on the prepared dataset and the result of it confirms that the deep learning models can be applied in order to detect social media sentiment patterns. The produced system takes the tweet in as an input and gives the sentiment prediction in real time in the web application.

This designed sentiment analysis system is an effective classification for tweets using deep learning techniques into their sentiment polarities. The classification classifies the given tweets into positive, negative and neutral sentiment.

From result shows that deep learning techniques may be applicable to large social media data and for feature extraction based on their sentiments.

Fig. 2. Main dashboard interface of the proposed Twitter Sentiment Analysis system.

It implements a web-based dashboard from where a user can access the features of the system which include Manual Tweet Analysis, Uploading Dataset, Visualization of Analytics, View Prediction History, About Model, etc.

Fig. 3. Sentiment analytics dashboard showing distribution of predicted sentiments.

You get all the information from the sentiment classification system on this dashboard. It displays the count of positive, negative and neutral predictions predicted and also graphs as a pie chart and bar graph for more visual analysis.

Fig. 4. Model information interface displaying dataset, architecture, and training details.

In addition, a model information interface is given where it indicates the dataset on which it was trained and the deep learning architecture used, the training parameters. The model of sentiment classification is implemented on LSTM networks which can properly classify sequence text in natural language processing task.

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
Logistic Regression	78.4%	77.9%	76.8%	77.3%
Naïve Bayes	74.6%	73.5%	72.9%	73.2%
SVM	82.3%	81.7%	80.5%	81.1%
Proposed LSTM Model	89.5%	88.7%	88.1%	88.4%

Table I. Performance comparison of sentiment classification models

Table I compares the performance results of different ML and DL models for sentiment classification. It can be seen that general machine learning methods (e.g. Naive Bayes, Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine) can achieve a certain performance for sentiment classification. The designed LSTM-based deep learning model performs better as it can learn the contexts and sequential dependencies in the text data. From the experimental result, it is obvious that LSTM model has achieved high accuracy, precision, recall and F1 score.

V. LIMITATIONS OF THE SYSTEM

Though the results generated by the suggested sentiment analysis model have been quite successful, there are still few shortcomings. The model is possibly not as well performing as it ought to be when analyzing tweets with sarcasm and vagueness, which will significantly affect how it determines the tweets' sentiment. The data used to train the model actually does not include enough variation in words and phrases to be representative of an actual social media account. Deeper deep learning models and more enormous datasets can be implemented into the model for further improvement.

VI. CONCLUSION

We have built Twitter sentiment analysis system with deep learning technique. The system is utilized to perform text classification into three sentiment categories (positive, negative and neutral) respectively. The integration of NLP techniques and deep learning model LSTM is the strength of our proposed approach in order to develop an effective tool to do text mining on social media. Different stages in the text analysis process were adopted and developed including data preprocessing, feature extraction, model training and sentiment prediction in order to optimize the sentiment classification. Users can also submit tweet text through a web interface and receive classified sentiment.

According to the experiment results, our proposed system has the capacity of mining and visualizing the overall

sentiment patterns of the Twitter data. Sentiment trends are represented by an analytics dashboard in graphical view such as bar charts, in order to provide users with an analysis of sentiments over classes. Overall, the system designed and built can offer a useful method of carrying out and understanding sentiment analysis for social media data in a huge volume, beneficial to any research institution or company who wants to analyse social media trends.

VII. FUTURE SCOPE

So, it has been shown that, with a deep learning based method such as the one described in this document, it is possible to carry out sentiment analysis for a tweet. However, there are several ways in which the system can be enhanced to carry out analysis of the meaning: For instance, one could use a larger corpus that is much larger than what was used here, so that the model could understand the variations in English writing styles, slangs and plain English words included in a tweet message.

. Advanced learning architectures such as transformer based language models (BERT, Roberta, and GPT models) may also be utilized in the architecture, since these have produced outstanding and best-of- breed results in Natural Language understanding and as a consequence may achieve a better level of accuracy with respect to the task of sentiment classification, and enable the system's better portability with respect to different populations of twitterers.

Finally, the system may also be integrated with live Twitter APIs to perform real-time sentiment analysis, where data are processed as they come into the system and trends as well as opinions for a product, event or a topical issue is observed by making use of dynamic visualizations and Dashboards.

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